

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE TECHNOLOGY OF CRITICAL THINKING IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract

The article describes the use of technology for the development of critical thinking in English lessons. Examples of effective techniques for the development of critical thinking are given. The positive aspects of this technology are given and the difficulties in using the technology for the development of critical thinking are indicated.

Keywords: *critical thinking, creativity, communicative competence, thinking, educational process*

One of the most interesting modern technologies in the field of education is the technology for the development of critical thinking. Critical thinking, i.e. creative, helps a person to determine his own priorities in his personal and professional life, involves taking individual responsibility for the choice made, increases the level of the individual culture of working with information, forms the ability to analyze and draw independent conclusions, predict the consequences of his decisions and be responsible for them, allows to develop a culture of dialogue in joint activities. These factors determine the relevance of the technology for the development of critical thinking [1]. In my lessons, I use the following techniques of critical thinking technology: cluster, true or false sentences; confused logical chains; role play; search for answers to the questions posed.

1. Cluster. When studying the topic "Flora and Fauna", students look at the cluster and try to determine the class of animals and the habitat of these animals. Next, students read the text and compare their assumptions with the information in the text. For example, to the question "Where do animals live?"

Clusters are used both at the stage of calling and at the stage of reflection; they can be a way of motivating mental activity before studying a topic or a form of systematizing information based on the results of passing the material. Depending on the goal, the teacher organizes individual independent work of students or collective activities in the form of a general joint discussion.

2. Table "Z-H-U" ("I know - I want to know - I learned.")

One of the ways of graphic organization and logical-semantic structuring of the material.

The form is convenient, as it provides for an integrated approach to the content of the topic.

Step 1: Before getting to know the text, students, independently or in a group, fill out the first and second columns "I know", "I want to know" [2].

Step 2: In the course of acquaintance with the text or in the process of discussing what has been read, the students fill in the "Found out" column.

Step 3: Summing up. When studying the topic "The United Kingdom of Great Britain", students before reading the text about Great Britain.

3. Catch the mistake. For the Adjectives topic, I use this exercise. When completing the assignment, mistakes are made on purpose in order to correct the sentences. For example, "Degrees of comparison of adjectives":

- 1) Cows are bigger than lions.
- 2) A tiger is angrier than a fox.
- 3) A giraffe is the more beautiful animal.
- 4) A monkey is funniest animal.
- 5) Elephants bigger than bears.
- 6) A crocodile longer than a fish

4. Keyword storytelling. At the lesson "The Republic of Kazakhstan. Geographical Position and Population" students compose a story on this topic. Thus, this makes it easier for them to compose sentences, as they see the approximate structure of the story [4].

5. Reading intermittently allows

- interest,
- engage in meaningful reading.

An example of working with the text "Environmental Problems".

Stage 1 - challenge. Why is the work exactly called? What environmental problems can you name in our world?

Teacher: Why is the text called "Environmental Problems"?

S1 - The text involves young generation to protect the world.

S2 - People forget about environment.

S3 - Environmental problems are the main problem in the world.

Teacher: What will be at the end?

S1 - I think the statistics are given.

S2 - To my mind, people call to protect the nature.

Stage 2 - comprehension. Reading the text in small passages with a discussion of the content of each and a forecast of the development of the plot.

The necessary stops are highlighted in advance in the text - depending on the size of the text. During these stops, questions are asked that encourage critical thinking. Emphasis should be placed on high-level issues.

Stage 3 - Reflection. Closing conversation. At this stage, the text again represents a single whole. The forms of work with students can be different: writing, conversation, joint search, choice of proverbs, creative work.

6. Thin and Fat Questions. Students are encouraged to formulate thin and thick questions to the topic. Further, the teacher determines the type of question. As you work with the table, questions are written in the left column that require a simple or monosyllabic answer. In the right column, questions are written that require a detailed, detailed answer. After the answers to these questions are voiced, students are invited to read or listen to the text, find confirmation of their assumptions and answers to the questions [5]. At the stage of comprehending the content, the technique serves to actively fix questions in the course of reading, listening; in reflection - to demonstrate understanding of the past. At the stage of reflection, the task is to compose another 3-4 thin and thick questions, enter them in the table, work with questions in pairs, choosing the most interesting ones that can be asked to the whole group.

At the lesson on the topic "Famous People of Kazakhstan" I invite students to talk about the biographies of writers (A. Kunanbaev).

When and where did he live?

Have you read any of his stories?

What were they about?

What were the characters like?

What do you know about him and his life?

7. Sinkwine.

Comes from the French word "cing" - five. This is a five-line poem. Used as a way to synthesize material. Laconic form develops the ability to summarize information, to express thoughts in a few meaningful words, succinct and concise expressions. Experience shows that cinquain can be useful as:

1) a tool for synthesizing complex information;

2) a method for assessing the conceptual baggage of students;

3) means of developing creative expressiveness.

In English lessons, the use of sinkwine helps to solve many different educational problems. Let us outline some of the possibilities of this technique.

Sinkwine as a technique for setting the topic of the lesson.

At the beginning of the lesson, on the blackboard sinkwine with the first line skipped, and the content of the other four lines, students try to formulate the theme of sinkwine. An example of use on the topic "Traditions":

1) traditions

2) popular, favorite,

3) to remember, to know, to respect,

4) tastes differ,

5) superstition.

Sinkwine as a generalization of the work on the text. At the same time, the pair organization of work seems to be the most effective. Each couple is given 3-4 minutes to compose a sinkwine, after which several resulting works are discussed and then combined into one of the clearest sinkwines. Subsequently, the final version is used as a support for retelling the studied text.

Sinkwine as a way to check homework. Here it is possible to organize the work as follows: while some students answer questions about the text, others make up a syncwine based on it. If the text has not been read beforehand, the poem will not work, since sinkwine requires a complete understanding of the topic.

Sinkwine as reinforcement of the newly learned vocabulary. At the end of the lesson, students are encouraged to recall which new lexical units were learned on the topic. The resulting work can again be used to compose a short story on the topic.

Thus, sinkwine is a technique for the development of critical thinking, which allows one to present educational material on a specific topic in a few words and achieve a deeper understanding of it. It can be used on absolutely any subject. He teaches children to find the most accurate words and concisely convey the meaning of the entire text in a concise form. Sinkwine enriches vocabulary, prepares for a short retelling, teaches you to formulate an idea (key phrase).

A wide variety of techniques and strategies provides a large field for action and reflection [6].

Techniques that I most often use in my lessons: tables, keywords, cluster, various techniques for predicting material, confused logical chains, associations. Some people like to present information in a creative, new way. Therefore, there is a need to implement differentiated and individual approaches. In the classroom, the material is delivered in doses, since not everyone can work at the same pace, not everyone has the same reading technique and level of language proficiency. I adapt some techniques of technology for my student body.

After analyzing the work on this technology, I came to the conclusion that there are pluses and difficulties in using the technology for the development of critical thinking. Pros of using technology to develop critical thinking: students learn:

- classify, evaluate, analyze,

- make decisions,

- work in groups and pairs,

- work with a large amount of information,

- highlight the main thing,

- express ideas in your own words,

- select important information from what you read, present it in a concise, concise form.

The technology for the development of critical thinking implements the principle of humanization and cooperation, promotes activity in the educational pro-

cess, activates thinking, increases interest, forms communication skills, and creates a psychologically comfortable environment in the classroom.

It is convenient to combine the technology for the development of critical thinking with other technologies: integrated lessons, problem-based, differentiated learning, ICT and Internet technologies, etc.

The technology of critical thinking is used in foreign language lessons and allows you to significantly increase the time of speech practice in the lesson for each student, to achieve the assimilation of the material by all group members, to solve various educational and developmental problems. The teacher, in turn, becomes the organizer of independent educational, cognitive, communicative, creative activities of students, teacher has opportunities to improve the language learning process, develop the communicative competence of students, the holistic development of their personality.

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